

Daodejing 道德經

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Daodejing 道德經 ("Classic of the Way and Virtue") is the title, fixed toward the end of the second century CE, attributed to a roughly 5000-character book, divided into 81 chapters, and recognized, together with the Zhuangzi 莊子, as the fundamental text for the philosophical tradition called "Daoism" (Daojia 道家) – as well as for the later religious movement called "religious Daoism" (Daojiao 道教). The text is also known by the name of its traditionally credited author, Laozi 老子 (the Old Master) or by the title Wuqianwen 五千文 ("Classic of the Five Thousands Characters"). The historicity of its author has long been a matter of scholarly discussion: the first biographical notes on his figure, mostly inconsistent with each other, date back to the 1st century BCE and are found within Sima Qian 司馬遷 (c. 145–86 BCE) historiographical work, the Shiji 史記. To date, most scholars believe that Laozi represents a legendary figure whose historicization was the result of an attempt to legitimize philosophical and meditative practices associated with Daoism, and that the text is a collection of passages put together by different editors and compilers rather than the work of a single hand. Both transmitted and unearthed versions of this text have come down to us and are characterized by varying degrees of variation: in the total number of characters, the division into chapters, the division into the two sections of Daojing 道經 ("Classic of the Way", chapters 1-37) and Dejing 德經 ("Classic of the Virtue", chapters 38-81) and the sequence of the two sections, lexical variations, etc. Of the versions transmitted by tradition, the main ones are known by the name of the commentary to which they are attached. To name the most credited, among almost a thousand commentaries known to date, a version transmitted together with the commentary written by the Sanguo 三國 period (220 to 280 AD) philosopher Wang Bi 王弼 (226-249 AD), called the Wang Bi version; the Heshang Gong 河上公 version, which enjoyed enormous authority, but whose dating is uncertain (hypotheses range from the 2nd century BCE to the 4th century CE); the Yan Zun 嚴遵 (59-24 BCE) version, which only includes the Dejing section of the text (the Daojing section apparently went lost between 1200 and 1445). As for the earliest reference to the Laozi, the earliest commentator on the text of which we are aware is the philosopher and intellectual Han Feizi (280-233 B.C.): two chapters of his work, entitled Jie Lao 解老 ("Commentary on the Laozi") and Yu Lao 喻老 ("Explanation of the Laozi"), comment on several chapters of the Laozi. The quoted passages are very close, though not identical to those found in the textus receptus. As for the unearthed sources, there have been several archaeological finds that have unearthed fragments and texts related to the Laozian textual tradition, including passages engraved on stone or jade and manuscripts on silk and bamboo. The most significant findings include manuscript versions found in Dunhuang 敦煌, Mawangdui 馬王堆 and Guodian 郭店. The so-called Xiang'er 想爾 edition of the Laozi, accompanied by the Xiang'er commentary to the text, has been recovered from the Buddhist grottoes of Dunhuang (Gansu) at the beginning of the twentieth century and only includes the Daojing section. The two archaeological discoveries at the Mawangdui site in 1973 and the Guodian site in 1993 contributed greatly to the understanding of the textual history of the Daodejing. In fact, two silk scrolls containing two almost complete copies of the Daodejing were unearthed at the Mawangdui site (Changsha, Hunan) in a tomb dated to 168 BCE, together with various philosophical and medical works. These texts, referred to as Text A (甲) and Text B (乙), distinguished by a few lexical differences, reverse the traditional order of the book's sections, having the Dejing section first and the Daojing section next. Regarding the find at the Guodian site (Jingmen, Hubei), in Tomb No. 1, dated around 300 BCE, these are three bamboo scrolls distinguished by different handwriting and bamboo strips, comprising a total of around one third of the transmitted Daodejing (about 1750 characters), with variations from the transmitted text in the lexicon, division of chapters, and the absence of the division into the Daojing and Dejing sections. Moreover, of the three scrolls, the so-called

scroll C has identical bamboo strip length, binding marks and handwriting from another text, titled Taiyi sheng shui 太一生水 – possibly originally bound together with Guodian Laozi C. The division into several scrolls of material closely related to the textual tradition of the Daodejing, together with the presence of another manuscript linked to one of the three scrolls, contributed to the understanding of what might have been the perception of the Daodejing as a unitary text in the third century BCE. Conceivably, the Daodejing did not stabilize as a unified text until the second century BCE, and even in the early imperial period it seems plausible that several different editions were circulating rather than one standard or official edition. As for the content of the work, the various chapters or stanzas (zhang 章) are heterogeneous in themes and vary in length. These contain maxims and aphorisms, written in partially rhymed prose. The traditional division into the two sections of Daojing and Dejing probably originates from the very fact that the first chapter of the Daojing section focuses on the concept of Dao 道 (Way), while the first chapter of the Dejing section focuses on the concept of De 德 (Virtue). In addition to the Dao as a cosmic, ineffable principle, not expressible through language, which governs the mechanisms of the cosmos, and the De, as a potency or virtue derived from the Dao itself, the Daodejing deals with several other issues: the concept of wuwei 無為 (avoidance of action), the opposition between being (you 有) and non-being (wuyou 無有), the cosmogonic process that brings about the emergence of the ten thousand things, the simplicity that recalls the uncarved wood (pu 樸), the sage person (shengren 聖人) that avoids action and is reluctant to war, the unity with the Dao, that is the ultimate achievement of the sage, as well as an anti-Confucian stance, which is most evident in the textus receptus but significantly less explicit in the manuscript version found in Guodian.

Date Range: 300 BCE - 2023 CE

Region: Han empires

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China

After the short-lived Qin dynasty (221–206 BCE), the Han empires (202 BCE–220 CE) were the second set of polities that ruled over the heartland of present-day China through a unified imperial system. The Liu clan who founded the Western Han (202 BCE–7 CE) emerged from the Chu region along the Yangzi River. Around the beginning of the 1st century CE, an affinal member of the imperial family seized power and founded the Xin Dynasty (9–23 CE). After a period of civil strife, a distant member of the Liu clan eventually founded the Eastern Han (25–220) that reunified the empire. The seat of the imperial house was moved from the western capital of Chang'an (modern-day Xi'an) to the eastern capital Luoyang.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Laozi Jicheng 老子集成. Vol.1-15 (eds. Xiong Tiejie 熊鐵基, and Chen, Hongxing 陳紅星) (2011). Peking: Zongjiao wenhua.
- Source 2: Jingmenshi Bowuguan 荊門市博物館, ed. (1998). Guodian Chumu zhujian 郭店楚墓竹簡. Peking:

Wenwu Press.

– Source 3: Gao Ming 高明, ed, (1996). Boshu "Laozi" jiaozhu 帛書老子校注. Peking: Zhonghua shuju.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/laozi/#Bib>

– Source 1 Description: Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/dao-de-jing>

– Source 1 Description: Daodejing

– Source 2 URL: <https://ctext.org/guodian>

– Source 2 Description: Guodian Laozi on bamboo

– Source 3 URL: <https://ctext.org/mawangdui>

– Source 3 Description: Mawangdui Laozi on silk

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Notes: The textus receptus was transmitted on paper, but there are manuscript editions of the Laozi written on different materials, for example, on silk scrolls in the case of the two manuscripts A and B found at the Mawangdui archaeological site, or on bamboo strips, as in the case of the three manuscripts (A, B, C) from Guodian.

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: Unspecified

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: There are several editions of the text, some of which are preserved in specific places. For example, the three Laozi found in Guodian are housed at the Jingmen City Museum (荊門市博物館). The two Mawangdui manuscripts are housed at the Hunan Province Museum (湖南省博物館).

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: Several editions of the text co-exist, so the answer varies by edition. None of the locations where texts related to the Daodejing tradition were found featured iconography related to the text itself, but some of these sites nonetheless featured iconography. The most striking case is that of the Dunhuang caves in Gansu province, which represent one of the finest examples of Buddhist-related art and iconography.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: The Daodejing is considered part of the so-called "Daoist Canon" of reference for Religious Daoism (Daojiao 道教).

Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Based on the partially rhymed structure of the text itself, scholars believe that the text

(or some of its sections) was transmitted orally in its earliest stage of transmission - prior to the earliest written records of which we have a track (Guodian Laozi dated around 300 B.C.). Moreover, as pointed out by I. Robinet 1977, the poetic form of the text suggests that it was believed that the text could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition of formulas and was intended to be memorized and sung.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– Yes

Notes: The authorship of the text is attributed to Laozi 老子 (Old Master), a semi-legendary figure whom classical historiography, beginning with Sima Qian's 司馬遷 *Shiji* 史記, dates back to the 6th century BCE. His biography is shrouded in legend: a contemporary of Confucius and a native of Chu 楚, Li 李 by surname, Er 耳 by given name, he allegedly served as archivist to the Zhou 周. As early as the early imperial period, with the mixing of native and Indian elements, a process of deification of the master began, which passed through the mythologizing of his biography: a legend was spawned concerning his miraculous birth, which occurred when he was already old and therefore wise, based on the very ambiguity of the name Laozi (old master/old child).

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

Notes: There are several editions of the text with sometimes significant variations in content, vocabulary, order of passages, and sections.

- ↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?
– No

- ↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?
– No

Notes: The Daodejing has been handed down through a philosophical-literary tradition, in several editions associated with commentaries on the text. In addition, several manuscript editions have been unearthed from imperial and pre-imperial tombs. As the text is also a benchmark for practitioners of the Daoist religious cult, they also contribute to the transmission of it.

- ↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?
– Yes

Notes: The Daodejing is counted among the texts that are part of the Daoist canon, the so-called (Zhengtong) Daozang (正統)道藏, i.e., the reference texts for the so-called Religious Daoism, believed to have emerged around the 1-2 century CE.

- ↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?
– Yes

- ↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?
– Yes

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The Daodejing is not written in a sacred or religious language, but both the rhymed structure and the expressive complexity of the text, both linguistically and in terms of content, affect the mysticism of the book.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Notes: I. Robinet 1991 claims that the poetic form of the text suggests that it was believed that it could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition of formulas and was intended to be memorized and sung.

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: I. Robinet 1991 claims that the poetic form of the text suggests that it was believed that it could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition of formulas and was intended to be memorized and sung.

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Notes: I. Robinet 1991 claims that the poetic form of the text suggests that it was believed that it could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition of formulas and was intended to be memorized and sung.

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: Since the first/second century AD, the Daodejing has been taken as a reference text for the religious cults and ritual practices associated with Daoism.

- ↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ How often do the rituals take place?
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices?
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?
– Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?
– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Different versions of the text have come down to us, along different lines of transmission, as well as various manuscripts that can be ascribed to this work. The various editions differ in the total number of characters, division into sections and chapters, content and vocabulary - although they clearly belong to the same textual tradition.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The Daodejing did not originate as part of a collection of texts, but later became part of the so-called "Daoist Canon."

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Philosophical

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: None of the previous

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 31 refers to funerary rites that have to be conducted for the deceased in a battle.

Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

A supreme high-god is present

– No

Notes: There is no supreme high god explicitly mentioned in the text.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The texts refers in a general way to different kinds of spirits: shen 神 and gui 鬼, for example in chapters 39 and 60. From the text it appears that gui can potentially harm humans, based on human behaviour.

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world
– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– Yes

Notes: The text explicitly names an important sacrifice celebrated in honor of spirits and ancestors, called Tai lao 大牢, in which cattle, pigs, and sheep were offered (see ch. 20).

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
– Specify: The text does not provide precise information about these spirits.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Organized hierarchically?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other organization of pantheon?
 - Specify: Not specified in the text.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: none.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The text itself does not guide divination practices. However, as S. Allan 2003 points out, the text refers to tools used in divination, such as the shipan 式盤 (cosmograph, diviner's board). In fact, the term shi 式 appears in three chapters of the transmitted Daodejing, always with the meaning of "cosmograph": chapters 22, 28 and 65.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Notes: The text does not advocate any particular virtues; in fact, it strongly distances itself from the so-called Confucian virtues (such as benevolence, dedication to study, righteousness, etc.). Nonetheless, the term De 德, which can be translated as "virtue," is central to the Daodejing: however, this indicates the virtue or potency derived directly from the Dao itself. According to Chapter 38 of the Daodejing, the one that opens the Dejing section of the text, the virtuous person does not need to show virtue, and the so-called Confucian virtues are identified with that which draws men away from Dao, the Way.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The text does not use fictive kinship terminology in reference to its readers, but uses the term mu 母 (mother) in reference to the Dao 道 itself. For example in chapter 1 that reads: 無名天地之始；有名萬物之母. On the use of the word mu 母 in the context of the Daodejing see: C. Cook 2015.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Notes: Chapter 75 points out that men suffer hunger because of the excessive tribute in grain demanded of them by rulers.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: Chapter 72 and chapter 75 are concerned with the welfare of the people, with regard to the scarcity of livelihood.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Education in China has been primarily restricted to males for centuries.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The text, in several passages, explicitly stands out against all forms of war and focuses on the avoidance of warfare, resorting to the principle of non-action (wuwei 無為).

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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